

ITA212, a lowland variety, also yields well in the high rainfall uplands. But it is susceptible to grain discoloration (left). Silica greatly reduced the disease (right).

goethite. Annual rainfall averages 2,500 mm.

Silica as sodium silicate was applied before sowing at 400 kg/ha. Control and treated plots received 60-26-50 kg NPK/ha.

Disease intensity was markedly reduced on silica-treated plots (see table). The greatest effect was in reducing grain discoloration (see figure) and neck blast. Varieties differ in inherent resistance to these diseases; generally, semidwarfs are most susceptible. However, all varieties tested benefited from silica application. □

White leaf streak disease on rice in India

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White leaf streak disease was first reported by Deighton and Shaw in Papua New Guinea in 1960. The causal organism was designated as *Rumularia oryzae*. Subsequently, the fungus was renamed *Mycovellosiella oryzae* (Deighton & Shaw) Deighton. In India *Mycovellosiella* (= *Ramularia*) was recorded on several dicotyledonous plants. Until now there has been no report of the occurrence of this genus on cereals except for sorghum in India.

The disease was noticed in the ricefields of RRS Chinsurah, in Sep-Oct 1984. Pronounced symptoms appeared on cv. Ratna in Oct during the milk to soft dough stage. The disease was again

recorded in March 1985 but at lower severity.

Initial spots on the leaves are 0.5-2.5 mm long and 0.5-1.0 mm wide, oblong, white to creamish white, delimited by narrow brown margins,

Cellular inclusions in rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)-infected rice

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GSV-infected TN 1 plants were collected 1 mo after inoculation for electron microscope observation. Ultrathin sections showed an association of two types of inclusions in GSV-infected plants. No similar structures were observed in healthy plants.

Fibrils grouped in bundles were abundant in mesophyll and phloem cells. The fibrillar inclusions were free either in the nucleus or in the cytoplasm

1. Fibrillar inclusions (fi) in nucleus (n) and cytoplasm of a mesophyll cell (35,000X). m = mitochondria.

2. Tubular inclusions (ti) associated with tiny particles in a sieve tube of GSV-infected rice leaf (35,000X). m = mitochondria. cw = cell wall. st = sieve tube.

amphigenous, and interveinal. They spread basipetally from the leaf tips in a linear manner. The spots gradually coalesce and form white streaks on both surfaces of the leaves. □

(Fig. 1) or bounded with membrane in the cytoplasm. Similar inclusions were also found in vacuole and chloroplasts.

Another type of inclusion observed in the sieve tube consisted of tubular structures associated with particles 18 nm in diameter (Fig. 2). The occurrence of tubular structures was less frequent than that of fibrillar inclusions.

Similar fibrillar inclusions were observed in plants infected with maize stripe virus, rice stripe virus, and rice hoja blanca virus. Those viruses are similar to GSV in morphology and vector-virus interactions. The four can be classified in the same group. □

Effect of neem oil on tungro (RTV) infection in susceptible and resistant varieties

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RTV-susceptible and resistant cultivars were inoculated using 1, 3, and 5 viruliferous green leafhoppers (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* per plant. Neem

Effect of neem oil on RTV infection in susceptible and resistant varieties inoculated using different numbers of insects. Coimbatore, India.

oil (5%) was applied to seedlings 2 h before inoculation.

Increasing the number of insects increased infection from 50 to 95% in susceptible ADT31 and from 5 to 35% in resistant TNAU831520 (see figure). In

ADT31, neem oil significantly reduced infection rates when 1 GLH was used for inoculation. A similar reduction was observed with inoculation using 3 or 5 GLH/plant.

All treated plants of TNAU831520 were free of infection when one GLH was used for inoculation. Neem oil reduced infection to 10% in resistant plants inoculated using 3 or 5 insects. □

Some pathological and physiological diseases of rice in Punjab

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In Punjab, rice is grown as a wet season crop May-Oct. With the release of high-yielding varieties IR8, Jaya, and PR106, the area under rice cultivation has increased from 258,000 ha in 1966-67 to 1,703,000 ha in 1985-86.

Samples of diseased rice plants received for diagnosis by PDC 1980-85 are shown in the table. Bacterial blight appeared in 71% of the samples in 1980, then its incidence declined to 1985, when it increased to 44% samples infected.

Sheath rot has threatened the most

Diseases in samples of rice in Punjab, India, 1980-85.

Disease	Diseased samples (%)					
	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985
Bacterial blight	71	28	13	10	10	44
Sheath rot	3	19	19	27	6	2
False smut	5	1	5	8	7	2
Sheath blight	4	7	5	3	3	1
Bacterial leaf streak	3	0	0	0	0	4
Acid rain	0	0	0	0	1	2
Zn deficiency	13	17	50	28	10	8
Fe deficiency	0	6	0	15	5	4
N deficiency	0	16	3	8	8	3

popular variety PR106. False smut has recently gained importance, with infection in 1-7.5% of the samples. Stem rot caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, considered to be very severe before the introduction of high-yielding varieties,

was conspicuously absent from the samples received. This could be due to rice - wheat rotation. Bacterial leaf streak appeared occasionally in 1980 and 1985. Blast and brown leaf spot seem unimportant now. □

Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of carbofuran against whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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We evaluated the antifeedant effect of sublethal levels of systemic insecticide carbofuran against WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath). Three treatments were tested: topically treating WBPH with carbofuran solutions in acetone, using a no-soil root-zone application to susceptible glasshouse-grown TN1 rice plants, and treating leaves of potted TN1 plants with acetone solutions using a fine brush. Recently emerged (3-5 d)

Table 1. Antifeeding effect of carbofuran on macropterous WBPH females.^a Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom.

Treatment method	Concentration	Quantity of amino acids in honeydew ^b (µg dry weight/female per 24 h)	Antifeeding response (%)
Leaf (µg/cm ²)	0.159	28.6 a	54.7
	0.079	33.7 a	46.9
	0.016	43.8 b	31.3
	0.0	63.9 c	
Topical (ng/female)	0.1	23.3 a	78.1
	0.02	34.5 a	67.6
	0.01	54.1 b	48.6
	0.002	77.9 c	25.7
	0.0	105.6 d	
Root zone (µM)	2.0	18.5 a	68.4
	1.5	23.0 b	59.7
	1.0	30.9 c	47.4
	0.5	36.2 d	36.8
	0.1	46.9 e	17.5
	0.0	56.8 f	

^a Within a treatment method, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P = 0.05 by Duncan's multiple range test. No mortality was observed with any concentration (i.e., less than 5% mortality). Temperature 26 ± 1°. ^b Mean of 3 replications: quantity of amino acids in honeydew measured colorimetrically using glutamic acid as standard.